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A Comprehensive Review of AC and DC Collection Grids Architectures in Marine Renewable Energy Sources: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract

The increasing global demand for renewable energy sources has led to the rapid development of marine renewable energy (MRE) technologies such as wave, tidal and ocean current energy. One of the crucial aspects of MRE systems is the collection of energy from the turbines and their transmission to the shore through a collection grid. The collection grid architecture can be either AC or DC based on the type of energy source and the location of the offshore farm. This paper provides a comprehensive review of AC and DC collection grids in MRE systems. It discusses the main characteristics and differences of these two architectures and analyzes their advantages and disadvantages. The review also includes recent developments in both AC and DC collection grids and their implementation in MRE systems.

Keywords: Marine Renewable Energy; AC Collection Grid; DC Collection Grid .

1. Introduction

The global demand for renewable energy has fueled the rapid advancement of marine renewable energy (MRE) technologies like wave, tidal, and ocean current energy [1]. While these sources offer significant potential to enrich the renewable energy landscape, effectively harnessing and transmitting energy from marine installations to the onshore grid presents unique challenges. Tidal energy solutions are pivotal for establishing a more resilient and secure energy system, capable of withstanding market fluctuations. The hostile ocean environment underscores the necessity for straightforward, cost-effective, and reliable power conversion architectures. Research has explored various collection and transmission grid architectures for marine-based renewables [2]. Historically, offshore renewable projects predominantly relied on AC systems for collection and transmission, yet the growing scale and distance of offshore energy farms have prompted the exploration of alternative designs. High Voltage DC (HVDC) transmission has emerged as a practical solution for larger offshore farms [3]. The diode rectifier (DR) architecture, gaining traction within the industry and research community, offers notable advantages over conventional voltage source converters, such as reduced transmission losses, smaller physical footprint, and increased cost-effectiveness, making it an appealing solution for converting AC to DC in offshore energy applications [4]. Challenges arise due to the variable

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Fig. 5 (a) Point-to-Point (b) Star (c) Ring.

3. **Ring Topology:** This topology involves looping cables, which introduces additional costs due to the required switches. It creates a circular arrangement for the interconnection of units.
4. **Star Topology:** In the star topology, units are grouped together using cables of similar rating, and the collected power is transmitted to the shore via higher-rated cables. This approach streamlines the connection process.

Table 1. Comparison of different AC collection grid architectures.

Aspects	Point-to-Point	Radial	Ring	Star
Topology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct connection from each unit to the main substation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linear structure with a single connection path. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Circular loop with multiple connections. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple units connected centrally.
Redundancy & Reliability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited • fault in a cable can disrupt a unit. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited • fault affects downstream units. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderate • faults may not disrupt the entire loop. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High • central hub reduces fault impact.
Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easier to control voltage at the main substation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easier to control but might face voltage drop concerns. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some control over voltage through loop paths. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central control over voltage distribution.
Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less • significant changes for adding units. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less • adding units require new connections. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderate • adding units through loop paths. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly • easier addition of new units.
Complexity & Cost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simpler design • Lower initial cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplicity for small installations • Potential voltage drops concerns. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderate • loop connections add cost. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Higher • more robust • potential cost savings in redundancy.
Suitability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable for small installations with minimal future expansion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable for small to medium-sized installations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable for medium-sized installations with potential expansion. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable for larger, complex, or expanding installations.

The choice of AC collection grid topology for wave/tidal energy sources depends on factors such as installation size, redundancy requirements, scalability, complexity, cost, and potential future expansions. Point-to-point and radial grids

are simpler and cost-effective for smaller installations, but they may lack redundancy and scalability. Ring grids offer moderate redundancy and some flexibility for medium-sized installations, while star grids provide the highest redundancy, flexibility, and scalability, making them suitable for larger, more complex, or expanding wave/tidal energy installations.

3. DC Collection Grid Architectures:

In this section, we delve into the realm of potential DC collection grid topologies. It's worth noting that, as of the authors' knowledge, commercial DC grids for offshore farms remain uncommon, especially for vast, distant installations where HVDC transmission to the shore is a prevalent practice. Despite this, the internal collection grids within these farms continue to rely on AC technologies. DC collection grids neatly fit into two main categories: parallel (Fig. 6 (a), (b)) and series topologies (Fig. 6(c)).

Fig. 6 (a) Single Stage Parallel DC (b) Double Stage Parallel DC (c) Series DC.

3.1 Parallel DC Collection Grids: These grids resemble AC radial topologies but with added redundancy through double-sided ring setups. One fundamental design connects energy converters directly to an onshore inverter via a feeder cable. More complex designs involve multiple feeder strings connected to a passive offshore point, offering redundancy for fault tolerance. This approach suits large farm systems but may incorporate offshore hubs for greater distances, albeit with increased complexity and cost.

Table 2. Comparison of different DC collection grid architectures.

Aspects	Parallel DC Collection Grids	Series DC Collection Grids
Redundancy & Reliability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher redundancy within branches. Independent operation of energy converters. Faults in one branch won't disrupt the whole system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vulnerable to faults within the series. A single fault can disrupt the entire grid. Requires added protective measures and fault detection.
Voltage Level & Transmission Distance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common voltage level, suitable for nearby converters. Voltage drops over longer distances without boosting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aggregates voltage across converters. Potential for higher transmission distances. Beneficial for offshore deployments.
Complexity & Cost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simpler implementation, independent converter operation. Potential cost savings in infrastructure and control systems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More complex design and maintenance. Requires specialized protection systems, insulation, and power fluctuation management. Higher initial and ongoing operational costs.
Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Easily scaled. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scalability challenges.

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| Suitability | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable for smaller installations incremental capacity increase. • Smaller installations. • Near-shore. • Better redundancy & simple. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adding converters string requires voltage and power management. • Larger offshore installations. • For long-distance transmission. • Fault management & voltage regulation. |
|--------------------|---|--|

3.2 Series DC Collection Grids: In this topology, energy converters are connected in series to achieve high voltage DC transmission, providing cost-effective long-distance transmission without the need for HVDC offshore platforms. However, insulation challenges arise, especially for the last energy converter in a string. Alternative solutions include series-connected offshore farm concepts with AC/AC conversion, HF transformers, and passive diode rectification, particularly useful for high-power-rated energy converters.

4. Other potential Architectures: To address size and weight challenges of an offshore converter, a high-voltage DR is suggested [11]. However, coordinating turbines in the offshore AC grid and achieving MPPT pose hurdles. Hence different variants with auxiliary devices (Fig. 7(a)) [12]. Another promising architecture which is being proposed is mesh connected architecture (Fig. 7(b)). The AC collector system transitioned to a mesh connection from parallel, significantly bolstering reliability on the collector side [13]. This alteration promotes a more robust and fault-tolerant configuration. The multiterminal direct current (MTDC) connection has emerged as a promising solution for seamlessly integrating offshore multi-use platforms into continental grids (Fig. 7(c)). This approach aims to efficiently leverage offshore resources, improve energy efficiency, and unify diverse functions such as renewable energy generation and aquaculture within a single platform. In [14] a multiterminal direct current (MTDC) connection is proposed for integration of offshore multi-use platforms into continental grids.

Fig. 7 (a) DR based DC collection (b) Mesh connected (c) Multiterminal Offshore Hybrid Energy Mix.

5. Conclusion

This paper provides a comprehensive review of AC and DC collection grids in MRE systems. The review highlights the advantages and disadvantages of both architectures and discusses recent developments and challenges in their implementation. The paper also highlights the importance of choosing the appropriate collection grid architecture based on the specific characteristics of the MRE system, such as the type of MRE device, the location of the device, and the distance between the device and the onshore substation. This review can serve as a useful resource for researchers, engineers, and policymakers involved in the development and optimization of MRE systems.

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